

**INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**
[ISSN: 0975-4725; CODEN(USA): IJPS00]
Journal Homepage: <https://www.ijpsjournal.com>

Research Article

In Silico ADME, Bioactivity, Toxicity Predictions and Molecular Docking Studies Of A Few Antidiabetics Drugs

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ARTICLE INFO

Published: 13 Feb. 2025

Keywords:

Computational tools, physicochemical properties, bioactivity, toxicity, docking.

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.14862825

ABSTRACT

Computer-aided drug design (CADD) methodologies have become essential in modern drug discovery, offering significant cost and time efficiency. By analyzing the physicochemical properties, bioactivity, and toxicity profiles of existing drugs, researchers can identify key pharmacophoric features crucial for designing novel compounds targeting specific biological pathways. In this study, 27 FDA-approved antidiabetic drugs (since 1957) were selected for computational analysis. Their physicochemical properties, bioactivity scores, and toxicological profiles were predicted using various tools, including Molinspiration, SwissADME, Osiris Properties Explorer, and pkCSM. Additionally, molecular docking studies were performed using CB-Dock against target proteins with PDB IDs: 4YVV, 5G5J, 5Y2T, 7Y1J, 6B1E, 2PDK, 5NN6, 7Y0B, and 3UA1. Among the selected compounds, 25 adhered to Lipinski's Rule of Five, suggesting good oral bioavailability. However, certain compounds exhibited toxicity risks, such as mutagenicity and tumorigenicity, as predicted by the Osiris Properties Explorer. Molecular docking facilitated the investigation of drug-target interactions, providing insights into binding mechanisms. These findings contribute to the rational design of novel antidiabetic drugs with improved efficacy and safety.

INTRODUCTION

Drug discovery and development is an intensive, interdisciplinary, and time-consuming process. Traditional drug discovery relies on experimental and empirical approaches, but advancements in

computational tools have significantly accelerated these processes. Figure 1 illustrates the stages of conventional drug discovery and the role of computer-aided drug discovery (CADD) in reducing development time.^{1,2}

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Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

Figure 1. Stages Of Traditional Drug Discovery and Computer-Aided Drug Design Tools

Drug failures often stem from poor efficacy, side effects, unfavourable pharmacokinetics, or commercial limitations.³ The increasing use of *in-silico* chemistry and molecular modeling has revolutionized drug design. Drug-likeness, a key concept in CADD, depends on molecular properties such as hydrophobicity, electronic distribution, hydrogen bonding, molecular size, and flexibility. Lipinski's Rule of Five (RO5) provides guidelines for assessing a molecule's pharmacokinetic properties, such as absorption, distribution, metabolism, and excretion (ADME).^{4,5} These properties can be predicted before synthesis, optimizing drug design efficiency. Molecular docking plays a crucial role in predicting drug-target interactions by simulating ligand binding orientations.⁶ Typically, the receptor remains rigid while ligand conformations adjust for optimal binding. Overall, computational tools have transformed drug discovery by enhancing efficiency, reducing costs, and enabling researchers to address complex challenges that traditional methods alone cannot efficiently resolve. Antidiabetic drugs effectively lower blood sugar levels, preventing complications like retinopathy, neuropathy, and nephropathy while alleviating symptoms such as excessive thirst, urination, and ketoacidosis. Diabetes is a carbohydrate metabolism disorder caused by

insulin deficiency or resistance, disrupting blood glucose regulation. Normal fasting blood glucose levels range between 70–100 mg/dL. Type 1 diabetes results from insulin deficiency and is treated with subcutaneous insulin injections. Type 2 diabetes, the most common form, arises from insulin resistance. Treatments aim to (1) stimulate insulin secretion, (2) enhance insulin sensitivity, (3) reduce glucose absorption, and (4) promote glucose excretion through urine.^{7,8} Numerous antidiabetic drugs on the market target different receptors. While many small molecules with antidiabetic potential have been identified and are undergoing clinical trials, their use is often limited by side effects. This highlights the need for new, potent antidiabetic agents with improved pharmacological profiles.⁹⁻¹² Prompted by above findings, a few US FDA approved antidiabetic drugs were selected and their *in silico* properties were determined by various computational tools to predict physicochemical properties, bioactivity, *in silico* binding affinity and toxicity profiles in the present investigation.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

Selection of compounds

US FDA approved antidiabetic agents (1-27) of various chemical categories were selected for the present investigation. The details of the same were provided in **Table 1** and **Figure 1**.

Table 1. Details of selected compounds

S. No.	Drug name	Chemical class	Molecular Formula	Year of FDA approval
1	Tolbutamide	Sulfonylureas	C ₁₂ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₃ S	1957
2	Glibenclamide	Sulfonylureas	C ₂₃ H ₂₈ ClN ₃ O ₅ S	1984
3	Glipizide	Sulfonylureas	C ₂₁ H ₂₇ N ₅ O ₄ S	1994
4	Gliclazide	Sulfonylureas	C ₁₅ H ₂₁ N ₃ O ₃ S	1998
5	Glimepiride	Sulfonylureas	C ₂₄ H ₃₄ N ₄ O ₅ S	1995
6	Chlorpropamide	Sulfonylureas	C ₁₀ H ₁₃ N ₂ O ₃ S	1958
7	Tolazamide	Sulfonylureas	C ₁₄ H ₂₁ N ₃ O ₃ S	1957
8	Acetohexamide	Sulfonylureas	C ₁₅ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₄ S	1964
9	Metformin	Biguanide	C ₄ H ₁₁ N ₅	1994
10	Rosiglitazone	Thiazolidinedione	C ₁₈ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₃ S	1999
11	Pioglitazone	Thiazolidinedione	C ₁₉ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₃ S	1999
12	Lobeglitazone	Thiazolidinedione	C ₂₄ H ₂₄ N ₄ O ₅ S	2013
13	Repaglinide	Meglitinide	C ₂₇ H ₃₆ N ₂ O ₄	2008
14	Nateglinide	Meglitinide	C ₁₉ H ₂₇ NO ₃	2000
15	Sitagliptin	DPP-4 inhibitors	C ₁₆ H ₁₅ F ₆ N ₅ O	2006
16	Saxagliptin	DPP-4 inhibitors	C ₁₈ H ₂₅ N ₃ O ₂	2009
17	Teneligliptin	DPP-4 inhibitors	C ₂₂ H ₃₀ N ₆ OS	2012
18	Alogliptin	DPP-4 inhibitors	C ₁₈ H ₂₁ N ₅ O ₂	2013
19	Linagliptin	DPP-4 inhibitors	C ₂₅ H ₂₈ N ₈ O ₂	2011
20	Sorbinil	Aldose reductase inhibitors	C ₁₁ H ₉ FN ₂ O ₃	2015
21	Acarbose	Alpha glucosidase inhibitors	C ₂₅ H ₄₃ NO ₁₈	1999
22	Miglitol	Alpha glucosidase inhibitors	C ₈ H ₁₇ NO ₅	1999
23	Dapagliflozin	SGLT-2 inhibitors	C ₂₁ H ₂₅ ClO ₆	2013
24	Canagliflozin	SGLT-2 inhibitors	C ₂₄ H ₂₅ FO ₅ S	2013

25	Empagliflozin	SGLT-2 inhibitors	$C_{23}H_{27}ClO_7$	2014
26	Ertugliflozin	SGLT-2 inhibitors	$C_{22}H_{25}ClO_7$	2017
27	Bromocriptine	Dopamine D2 agonist	$C_{32}H_{40}BrN_5O_5$	2009

DPP-4 inhibitor: Dipeptidyl peptidase 4 inhibitors; SGLT-2 inhibitor: Sodium-glucose co-transport 2 inhibitors

Figure 2. Chemical structures of selected compounds

<p>3. Glipizide</p>		
<p>6. Chlorpropamide</p>		
<p>9. Metformin</p>		
<p>12. lobeglitazone</p>		
<p>15. Sitagliptin</p>		

Prediction of physicochemical properties

Physicochemical properties of the selected antidiabetic drugs (1-27) were determined by online tools, such as Molinspiration web JME editor^{13,14} and SwissADME.¹⁵ Properties like molecular weight (MW), logP, hydrogen bond acceptors (HBA), hydrogen bond donors (HBD), molar volume (MV) were computed by using Molinspiration tool, while bioavailability and synthetic accessibility scores were determined using SwissADME.

Prediction of bioactivity studies

Bioactivity is predicted by molinspiration, is a measure of the ability of the drug molecule to

interact with different receptors, such as GPCR ligands, Kinase inhibitors, Protease inhibitors, Ion channel modulators, or to interact with enzymes and nuclear receptors. Larger the bioactivity score, higher is the probability that the proposed molecules will be active.¹²

Prediction of toxicity

Toxicity prediction of the selected drugs was attempted by using OSIRIS property explorer¹⁶ and pkCSM tools.¹⁷ Toxicity parameters, such as mutagenicity, irritancy, tumorigenicity and reproductivity of the selected antidiabetic drugs were predicted using OSIRIS property explorer software. This tool is not only useful for the

prediction of toxicity, but also for the determination of pharmacokinetic parameters, such as cLog P, solubility, molecular weight, drug-likeness. The predicted results are obtained with colour coding. Pk CSM is a machine learning platform which is useful for ADMET predictions. Parameters like maximum tolerance dose, lethal dosage (LD₅₀), hepatotoxicity and skin sensitization of the compounds **1-27** were predicted using pk CSM tool.

In silico molecular docking studies

Docking using CB Dock¹⁸

- CB-Dock was opened in the web browser.

- The ‘Dock’ option was selected.
- The required files for docking were selected-
 - Protein file in PDB format.
 - Ligand file in MOL or PDB format.
- The ‘Submit’ button was clicked.
 - In a few minutes, docking was completed and the results along with the structure were displayed.

Visualization using Biovia

- File → open → “docking complex.pdb” file.
- View → hierarchy → select docked complex file → ligand interaction → show 2D diagram.

Table 2. Details of target proteins selected for the studies

S. No.	Therapeutic category	PDB_ID	Resolution (Å)	Year of release
1.	Sulfonylureas	4YVV	2.30	2015
2.	Biguanide	5G5J	2.60	2017
3.	Thiazolidinedione	5Y2T	1.70	2017
4.	Meglitinide	7Y1J	3.00	2023
5.	DPP-4 inhibitors	6B1E	1.77	2017
6.	Aldose reductase inhibitors	2PDK	1.55	2008
7.	Alpha glucosidase inhibitors	5NN6	2.00	2017
8.	SGLT-2 inhibitors	7Y0B	2.08	2023
9.	Dopamine D2 agonist	3UA1	2.15	2011

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

For the selected 27 antidiabetic drugs physicochemical properties, bioactivity scores, toxicity parameters and were predicted using different *in silico* techniques. The physicochemical properties determined by using molinspiration and SwissADME tools were provided in **Table 3**. Twenty five out of twenty seven compounds were found to obey Lipinski Rule of Five (RO5) as per the results displayed in **Table 3**. As per RO5, Acarbose and

Bromocriptine have showed a greater number of violations (high MW, Log P, HBD and HBA), indicating their poor oral absorption. Remaining drugs were showing zero violation, indicating their good oral absorption as per the predictions. Drug-likeness score was found maximum in case of Tenelegliptin among the evaluated compounds. A positive drug score indicates the predominance of the pharmacophoric moieties in the molecule. All the compounds showed a positive value in the drug score calculation and were in the range of 0.10 -

0.98. Greater drug score was observed for the drugs Miglitol, Sorbinil and Rosiglitazone.

Table 3. Physicochemical properties of selected antidiabetic drugs (1-27)

S.N O	Drugs	Log P	TPSA	MW	HB A	HB D	Violation	nR	MV	Drug likeness	Drug score
1	Tolbutamide	2.54	75.27	270.35	5	2	0	5	242.79	-1.19	0.13
2	Glibenclamide	4.77	113.60	494.01	8	3	0	8	424.74	4.53	0.66
3	Glipizide	2.31	130.15	445.55	9	3	0	7	393.90	3.39	0.80
4	Gliclazide	1.45	78.50	323.42	6	2	0	3	284.59	-7.85	0.10
5	Glimepiride	3.81	124.67	490.63	9	3	0	7	445.90	9.66	0.69
6	Chlorpropamide	2.21	75.27	276.75	5	2	0	4	222.96	7.63	0.20
7	Tolazamide	1.35	78.50	311.41	6	2	0	3	278.58	-2.38	0.15
8	Acetohexamide	2.46	92.34	324.40	6	2	0	4	284.80	1.43	0.53
9	Metformin	-1.13	88.99	129.17	5	5	0	3	126.83	3.59	0.35
10	Rosiglitazone	2.35	71.53	357.44	6	1	0	7	314.51	9.14	0.90
11	Pioglitazone	3.07	68.30	356.45	5	1	0	7	318.53	5.02	0.86
12	Lobeglitazone	3.60	102.89	480.55	9	1	0	10	416.30	6.81	0.81
13	Repaglinide	4.87	78.87	452.60	6	2	0	10	442.52	-2.72	0.40
14	Nateglinide	2.56	66.40	317.43	4	2	0	6	316.03	14.81	0.45
15	Sitagliptin	2.06	77.05	407.32	6	2	0	5	311.65	-9.16	0.43
16	Saxagliptin	1.24	90.35	343.47	5	3	0	2	327.22	-1.78	0.53
17	Teneligliptin	1.62	56.64	426.59	7	1	0	4	393.44	10.04	0.84
18	Alogliptin	0.25	97.06	339.40	7	2	0	3	311.64	-2.53	0.50
19	Linagliptin	2.25	116.88	472.55	10	2	0	4	427.73	1.30	0.69
20	Sorbinil	0.86	67.43	236.20	5	2	0	0	189.16	3.01	0.95
21	Acarbose	-5.51	321.16	645.61	19	14	3	9	544.93	-2.15	0.30
22	Miglitol	-2.79	104.38	207.23	6	5	0	3	189.18	4.27	0.98
23	Dapagliflozin	2.60	99.38	408.88	6	4	0	6	359.29	-0.68	0.58
24	Canagliflozin	3.92	90.15	444.52	5	4	0	5	387.02	-2.70	0.41

25	Empagliflozin	2.32	108.61	450.92	7	4	0	6	391.31	-2.68	0.43
26	Ertugliflozin	2.35	108.61	436.89	7	4	0	6	373.59	-0.41	0.35
27	Bromocriptine	5.01	97.98	650.62	9	2	2	5	548.72	6.81	0.27

The bioactivity data determined by molinspiration and the bioavailability score and moderate accessibility score determined from SwissADME tools were given in **Table 4**. The GPCR ligand activity of Bromocriptin was found to be moderate (0.51) among the tested anti diabetic drugs. Highest Protease inhibition was observed for Saxagliptin (1.11), Teneagliptin, Nateglinide and Sitagliptin. The enzyme inhibitory activity of the selected antidiabetic drugs was in between the range of -1.59 to 0.44. The poor bioavailability of Acarbose is observed in the predictions, which

may be due to its high molecular weight, HBA and HBD values (**Table 3 and 4**). The significance of synthetic accessibility score is to determine the ease of synthesis of compounds. The scale ranges from 1-10. The value towards 1 denotes that the compound can be easily synthesized and the value approaching to 10 denotes its difficulty in the synthesis. The predicted synthetic accessibility data are in the range of 2.37 – 7.25. The ease of synthesis of Chlorpropamide was evidenced in the predictions, as its score showed the least value (2.37) among all.

Table 4. Bioactivity, bioavailability and synthetic accessibility data predicted for selected antidiabetic drugs (1-27)

S.no	Drugs	GPCR Ligand	Ion channel modulator	Kinase inhibitor	Nuclear receptor ligand	Protease inhibitor	Enzyme inhibitor	Bioavailability score	Synthetic accessibility
1	Tolbutamide	0.04	-0.12	-0.60	-0.63	0.14	0.13	0.55	2.42
2	Glibenclamide	0.20	-0.07	-0.26	-0.31	0.25	0.06	0.55	3.34
3	Glipizide	0.31	-0.01	-0.17	-0.40	0.39	0.16	0.55	3.33
4	Gliclazide	0.19	-0.35	-0.34	-0.37	0.17	0.01	0.55	3.52
5	Glimepiride	0.15	-0.09	-0.37	-0.28	0.32	0.24	0.55	4.71
6	Chlorpropamide	0.02	-0.06	-0.66	-0.75	0.07	0.11	0.55	2.37
7	Tolazamide	0.06	-0.37	-0.24	-0.41	0.16	0.07	0.55	2.76
8	Acetohexamide	0.14	-0.10	-0.48	-0.47	0.28	0.11	0.55	2.58

9	Metformin	-1.44	-0.81	-2.47	-3.48	-1.11	-1.59	0.55	3.02
10	Rosiglitazone	0.15	-0.65	-0.61	0.35	-0.21	-0.07	0.55	3.35
11	Pioglitazone	0.25	-0.51	-0.71	0.64	-0.09	0.05	0.55	3.46
12	Lobeglitazone	0.11	-0.35	-0.54	0.38	-0.14	0.04	0.55	4.15
13	Repaglinide	0.14	-0.03	-0.33	0.03	0.07	-0.09	0.56	3.89
14	Nateglinide	0.34	0.12	-0.30	0.08	0.59	0.16	0.85	3.22
15	Sitagliptin	0.25	-0.27	0.01	-0.60	0.56	-0.06	0.55	3.50
16	Saxagliptin	0.42	0.07	-0.15	-0.04	1.11	0.20	0.55	5.02
17	Teneligliptin	0.35	0.18	0.03	-0.40	0.72	-0.10	0.55	4.30
18	Alogliptin	0.24	-0.27	-0.08	-0.20	0.12	0.12	0.55	3.51
19	Linagliptin	0.33	-0.53	-0.37	-1.04	0.19	0.04	0.55	4.40
20	Sorbinil	-0.59	-0.17	-0.01	-0.91	-0.32	-0.04	0.55	3.27
21	Acarbose	-0.02	-0.49	-0.33	-0.29	0.21	0.21	0.17	7.25
22	Miglitol	-0.41	-0.10	-0.53	-0.82	0.11	0.36	0.55	3.17
23	Dapagliflozin	0.15	-0.07	-0.05	0.09	0.06	0.25	0.55	4.52
24	Canagliflozin	0.15	-0.21	0.15	0.07	0.02	0.33	0.55	4.99
25	Empagliflozin	0.27	-0.12	0.12	-0.07	0.28	0.44	0.55	4.87
26	Ertugliflozin	0.22	0.12	-0.13	0.23	-0.07	0.28	0.55	5.54
27	Bromocriptine	0.51	-0.41	-0.31	-0.50	0.20	-0.17	0.55	6.39

The toxicity predictions determined for the selected drugs using OSIRIS property explorer and pkCSM tools were provided in **Table 5**. The

toxicity scores predicted by Osiris property explorer were color-coded, where green indicates probable activity. Properties with high risks of

undesired/toxic effects such as mutagenicity, tumorigenic, etc are shown in red, the compounds with mild toxic effects are indicated as orange, while the drugs with low probability of such effects are indicated as green colour.

Table 5. Toxicity data predictions using Osiris property explorer and pk CSM tools

S. No.	Drugs	Mutagenic	Tumorigenic	Irritant	Reproductive effect	LD ₅₀	Hepatotoxicity	Skin sensitivity	Maximum tolerance dose
1	Tolbutamide	Red	Red	Green	Red	2.067	No	No	1.333
2	Glibenclamide	Green	Green	Green	Green	1.71	Yes	No	-0.05
3	Glipizide	Green	Green	Green	Green	1.78	Yes	No	0.043
4	Gliclazide	Green	Red	Red	Red	2.181	Yes	No	0.033
5	Glimepiride	Green	Green	Green	Green	1.942	Yes	No	-0.479
6	Chlorpropamide	Red	Red	Green	Red	2.335	No	No	1.191
7	Tolazamide	Red	Orange	Green	Red	2.577	Yes	No	0.452
8	Acetohexamide	Green	Orange	Green	Orange	2.248	Yes	No	0.375
9	Metformin	Red	Green	Green	Red	2.453	No	Yes	0.902
10	Rosiglitazone	Green	Green	Green	Green	2.692	Yes	No	0.066
11	Pioglitazone (withdrawn)	Green	Green	Green	Green	2.258	Yes	No	0.41
12	Lobeglitazone	Green	Green	Green	Green	2.448	No	No	0.292
13	Repaglinide	Green	Green	Green	Green	2.51	Yes	No	0.452
14	Nateglinide	Green	Green	Green	Green	2.127	No	No	0.141
15	Sitagliptin	Green	Green	Green	Green	2.732	Yes	No	-0.59
16	Saxagliptin	Green	Green	Green	Green	2.835	Yes	No	-0.436
17	Teneligliptin	Green	Green	Green	Green	2.868	Yes	No	-0.833
18	Alogliptin	Green	Green	Green	Green	2.421	Yes	No	-0.327
19	Linagliptin	Green	Green	Green	Green	2.62	Yes	No	0.7
20	Sorbinil	Green	Green	Green	Green	2.187	No	No	0.519

21	Acarbose	Green	Green	Green	Green	1.589	No	No	0.538
22	Miglitol	Green	Green	Green	Green	4.13	No	No	2.239
23	Dapagliflozin	Green	Green	Green	Green	2.475	No	No	0.507
24	Canagliflozin	Green	Green	Green	Green	2.454	No	No	0.482
25	Empagliflozin	Green	Green	Green	Green	2.554	No	No	0.25
26	Ertugliflozin	Red	Green	Green	Green	2.633	No	No	0.264
27	Bromocriptine	Green	Green	Green	Red	3.739	No	No	-0.915

The mutagenic and the tumorigenic effects of the drugs (1-27) were found to be almost negligible, except for Tolbutamide, Gliclazide, Chlorpropamide, Tolazamide, Metformin, Ertugliflozin. The irritant effect of the drug Gliclazide was found to be significant among all. Among the tested drugs Tolbutamide, Gliclazide, Chlorpropamide, Tolazamide, Metformin and Bromocriptine have shown the reproductive effects. Fourteen out of twenty seven drugs have shown the hepatotoxicity. The LD₅₀ values were found to be in the range of 1.589-4.13. *In silico* molecular docking studies of the selected antidiabetic drugs was performed by using freely

available tool CB Dock. The target proteins were selected from PDB, depending on the mode of action of specific antidiabetic drugs. The target protein for each antidiabetic drug and binding energies of the resulting protein-drug complex were provided in **Table 6**. As per the docking poses represented in **Figure 2**, both the Thiazolidinedione drugs (Rosiglitazone) Pioglitazone) binding with amino acid residues Arginine 288, Serine 342, Lysine 265 on the active site of 5Y2T. Among the drugs docked against 4YVV, Glimepiride has shown highest binding energy (-11.9 Kcal/mol).

Table 6. Binding energies of selected drugs using CB Dock

Compound code	Drugs	Category -Target protein PDB-ID	Binding energy (kcal/mol)
01	Tolbutamide	Sulfonylureas – 4YVV	-7.6
02	Glibenclamide		-11.3
03	Glipizide		-11.1
04	Gliclazide		-10.8
05	Glimepiride		-11.9
06	Chlorpropamide		-7.8
07	Tolazamide		-10.1
08	Acetohexamide		-10.2
09	Metformin	Biguanide – 5G5J	-5.1
10	Rosiglitazone	Thiazolidinediones – 5Y2T	-8.5
11	Pioglitazone		-8.7
12	Lobeglitazone		-9.9
13	Repaglinide	Meglitinide – 7Y1J	-8.8
14	Nateglinide		-8.5
15	Sitagliptin	DPP-4 Inhibitors – 6B1E	-8.7
16	Saxagliptin		-7.2

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HOW TO CITE: B. V. Malavika, T. S. Ramya, Swathi Naraparaju*, In Silico ADME, Bioactivity, Toxicity Predictions and Molecular Docking Studies Of A Few Antidiabetics Drugs, *Int. J. of Pharm. Sci.*, 2025, Vol 3, Issue 2, 924-937. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14862825>

